

How Places Influence Public Sentiment and Social Interaction: An Exploratory Study Using Twitter and Census Data

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January 7, 2022

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Abstract

The goal of this study is to explore how geography influences social interaction and sentiment on social media. Data from the 2011 UK Census was combined with 63,375 geolocated tweets were linked to 106 community areas in the Leeds district. The findings show correlation between sentiment and differences in age, education, and employment but no with ethnicity and length of residency in a certain place. In homogeneous community regions, there is a higher proportion of positive sentiment. Public mood varies geographically throughout distinct community regions of Leeds district, UK. The new social media data can potentially reveal underlying patterns of social relationships for community development decision-making, especially, when combined with traditional Census data.

Keywords: Social interaction, social media, sentiment, demographics, communities

1. Introduction

The relationship between public emotion expressed on social media and local community geography is a growing field of research (Gallegos *et al.*, 2016; Lansley and Longley, 2016; Arthur and Williams, 2019). The use of new social media data sources as an alternative or complement to traditional data to quantify the general well-being of places has sparked interest in recent literature (Gibbons *et al.*, 2019; Voukelatou *et al.*, 2020). Social media data, according to Hollander *et al.* (2016), provides rich textual information regarding public beliefs, attitudes and behaviours. Facebook, Twitter and other social media has created a sense of community that transcends geographical boundaries (Gruzd *et al.*, 2011). However, The willingness of to use social media varies depending on socio-demographic factors in different communities (Williams *et al.*, 2017). Investigation of the underlying socioeconomic and demographic elements impacting public views on social media, on the other hand, is uncommon (Rahman *et al.*, 2020). This study investigates the relationship between sentiments expressed on Twitter and local community structural factors in order alleviate this constraint.

2. Data and methods

2.1 Data

Twitter data used in this study, was collected using the Twitter streaming API (<https://dev.twitter.com/streaming/public>) within the geographical bounding box of Leeds (upper left (-1.29, 53.94) and lower right (-1.80, 53.69)). Twitter data was pre-processed to remove unwanted noise (such as url, stopwords, punctuations, and so on).

The socio-demographic variables (age distribution, ethnicity, employment, educational attainment and length of residence) used are primarily from the Census 2011 figures (Table 1), available on UK data service (<http://infuse.ukdataservice.ac.uk/>) and chosen based on literature. The corresponding components of those variables were included to measure diversity metrics (see Gulma *et al.*, 2019). Census information can be merged with social media data to explain a social phenomenon, according to Vargo and Hopp (2017). All variables were collected at the lower super output area (LSOA) level and then aggregated into 106 Leeds community areas (Figure 1) (Stillwell and Phillips, 2006).

Table 1. Census variables used in the study.

Component	Standard Variable	Diversity Variable
Age distribution	Number of young persons (16-24)	Age diversity
Identity	Ethnic minority population	Ethnic diversity
Affluence / wealth	Age 16-64 economically inactive	Diversity of employment type
Educational attainment	Age 16 over no qualification	Diversity of educational attainment
Residential instability	Resident less than 2 years	Length of residence diversity

community name	community name
1 Adel	54 Hunslet / Stourton
2 Allerton Bywater & Gt and Lt Preston	55 Hyde Park
3 Alwoodley & Wgton Moor	56 Hipsley
4 Ardsley East / West (inc. Tingley)	57 Hk Hall
5 Armley	58 Woodhouse
6 Arthington & Pool	59 Lofthouse & Robin Hood
7 Bardsey & East Kewick	60 Marston
8 Barwick & Scholes	61 Meanwood
9 Beeston	62 Methley
10 Beeston Hill	63 Middlefield
11 Belle Isle	64 Middleton
12 Boston Spa	65 Moor Allerton
13 Bramham	66 Moortown
14 Bramhope	67 Morley North
15 Bramley	68 Morley South
16 Burley	69 New Farnley
17 Burley Lodge & Little Woodhouse	70 New Wortley
18 Burmantofts, Lincoln Green & Ebor Gardens	71 Oakwood
19 Calverley	72 Osmondthorpe
20 Chapel Allerton	73 Otley
21 Chapelwau	74 Oulton & Woodlesford
22 Churwell	75 Priestthorpe
23 City Centre	76 Pudsey
24 Cottingham & Linton	77 Pudsey Lowtown
25 Colton	78 Rawdon
26 Cookridge	79 Richmond Hill
27 Cottingley	80 Rothwell
28 Crossgates	81 Roundhay
29 Diggington	82 Sandhills, Gomers & Moor
30 East Bank	83 Thorne
31 Fairbank	84 Scott Hall & Miles Hill
32 Far Headingley	85 Seacroft North
33 Farnley	86 Seacroft South
34 Farsley & Rodley	87 Shadwell
35 Farsville	88 Stanningley
36 Garforth East	89 Seacroft
37 Garforth West	90 Swillington
38 Gildersome	91 Swinnow & Fairfields
39 Gipton North	92 Tinsill
40 Gipton South	93 Upper Armley
41 Gulsley	94 Upper Wortley
42 Hailton / Whitkirk	95 West Park
43 Hailton Moor	96 Wetherby
44 Harehills	97 Whitmoor
45 Harehills Triangle	98 Wortley
46 Harewood and District	99 Wythers
47 Hawthorpe	100 Yeadon
48 Headingley	101 Leddon & Ledsham
49 Holbeck	102 Aberford
50 Holt Park	103 Scarcroft
51 Horsforth	104 Cross Green
52 Horsforth Newalls & Woodside	105 Little London
53 Horsforth West End	106 Ireland Wood

Figure 1 Leeds community areas, 2001. Source: Stillwell and Phillips (2006)

2.2 Method

This study, use different reliability tests to examine the accuracy of human annotation and to compare the effectiveness of automated classification. Human annotatore were also employed through the Amazon Mechanical Turk (AMT) , a commercial crowdsourcing platform.

3. Results

The correlation between Twitter sentiments, diversity and standard variables are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Spearman’s correlations between Twitter sentiments, diversity and standard variables

Diversity variables					
Twitter sentiment	Ethnic diversity	Age diversity	Educational diversity	Length of residence diversity	Employment diversity
	.066	.341**	-.296**	.080	.228*
p-value	.500	.000	.002	.415	.019
Standard variables					
Twitter sentiment	Ethnic minority	Age 16-24	16 over no qualification	Length of residence < 2yrs	Age 16-64 economically inactive
	.110	-.052	.049	.111	-.017
p-value	.263	.599	.621	.259	.861

*correlation significant at 0.05 level (95% confidence); **correlation significant at 0.01 level (99% confidence)

As seen in Table 2, there is a significant but weak correlation between sentiment expressed in Twitter and diversity of age, education and employment. However, there was no significant correlation between Twitter sentiment and standard variables.

Table 3 shows the IRR results based on workers score before applying exclusion criteria, the accuracy and reliability of the manually classified tweets and algorithm classification were compared to see how much the results will differ if the exclusion criteria are applied. This decision was made in order assess the quality of inter-annotator results and to facilitate comparisons between human annotations and algorithm classification.

Table 3. Inter-rater reliability test between human annotators and algorithm

Inter-annotator			
Fleiss (κ)	Interpretation	Cronbach’s (α)	Interpretation
.312	Fair agreement	.775	Good agreement
Algorithm and human average			
.445	Moderate agreement	.770	Good agreement

IRR analysis between ternary and binary classifications is presented in Table 4. The results indicate that when sentiment is classified into binary (positive and negative), the accuracy of validation increases compared to where scores are classified into ternary (positive, negative and neutral). This suggests that excluding the neutral class from IRR evaluation could increase overall measurement accuracy (see Bouazizi and Ohtsuki, 2017).

Table 4. Comparisons of binary and ternary scores between human average and algorithm

Algorithm versus human average	
Cronbach's (α)	Interpretation
.645 (ternary)	Moderate agreement
.769 (binary)	Good agreement

Overall, when compared to human annotation, our method shows strong agreement for binary analysis ($\alpha = .769$) and moderate agreement for ternary analysis ($\alpha = .645$), which is slightly lower than the benchmark of .70. This is comparable to Provoost *et al.* (2019) $\alpha = .55$ value. Other studies have indicated slightly higher ($\alpha = .73$) (Sloan and Morgan, 2015). Nonetheless, the validation analysis conducted in this study indicates that the results of our sentiment algorithm are good and may be beneficial for further investigation

5. Discussion

The finding in this study is consistent with previous studies that found relationships between the public sentiment on Twitter and socio-demographic characteristics (age distribution, employment and educational attainment) (e.g Mitchell *et al.*, 2013; Bertrand *et al.*, 2013). For example, we found that ethnically more homogeneous community areas of Leeds (Figure 1) with a low diversity score such as Allerton Bywater, Kippax and Otley have a higher share of positive Twitter sentiment. Strong social networks in those local community areas are most likely. Previous studies have found that ethnically homogeneous communities are more likely to have strong social interactions and establish cohesion than ethnically diverse communities (Laurence and Bentley, 2016).

6. Conclusion

This study used new social media data (Twitter) and traditional 2011 UK census data to investigate how different community characteristics influence public mood. Data gathered from Twitter may not be a good reflection of general population, but it might be valuable for gaining a better knowledge of community social interaction.

Acknowledgement

The author wishes to thank the UK data service and Professor John Stillwell for permitting me to replicate his work on Leeds community areas in this study.

Author biography

Dr. Usman Lawal Gulma is of the Department of Geography, Adamu Augie College of Education, Argungu, Kebbi State, Nigeria. He holds a PhD in Geography from the University of Leeds, UK with interest in spatial analysis, data science and data mining. Usman has authored and co-authored a number of publications in peer-reviewed journals and presented papers at GISRUK conferences since 2015.

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